

AN APPRAISAL OF HEALTH STATUS IN SOLAPUR CITY

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article History: Received: 26th Sep 2025 Accepted: 10th Oct 2025 Published: 25th Oct 2025</p>	<p>The present study evaluates the overall health status of Solapur City with special reference to the facilities, services, and challenges within the Civil Hospital system. Health, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), encompasses physical, mental, and social well-being. The research uses both field survey data and secondary sources to analyze the biological, demographic, social, and cultural indicators of health among the urban population. Major health issues identified include orthopedic disorders, stomach ailments, women's health complications, malaria, cancer, and HIV, along with their preventive measures. The study also highlights the vital role of social workers in promoting health education, awareness, and social responsibility. It concludes that the Civil Hospital of Solapur plays a significant role in delivering quality healthcare but requires further improvements in resources, awareness programs, and social participation.</p>
<p>Keywords: Health Indicators, Solapur City, Civil Hospital, Social Work,</p>	

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2. According to Human Geography Dictionary Meaning of health,

"Referred to as in depth analysis of demographic component, classification of diseases and its distribution and health care systems."

3. According to Oxford dictionary the health is,

"Define as the state of bring free from illness or injury; a person's mental or physical condition."

4. The health indicates is total fitness of body and mind. Study Area Study Area

For this paper presentation we did the survey of civil hospital in solapur city.

Indicators of health

- Biological Indicators** - In biological indicators of health includes maturity, birth rate, fertility, lifespan.
- Demographic Indicators** - Demographic indicators includes population, growth, natural growth, fertility, mortality, and migration.
- Social Indicators** - Social indicators includes nutrition, medical facility, incident of disease, public health.
- Cultural and Economic Indicators** - Cultural indicators consist diet, standard of living, life style, traditions and customs of living.

Table 1.1 Name Diseases and Solution

Sr. No	Name of Disease	Causes of Diseases	Solution of Diseases
1	Orthopedic Disease	Due to lifting of heavy weight in small age by children and woman	To take a diet which help to increate calcium in the bone. Ex. Milk, ground nuts etc.
2	Stomach Disease	There are many causes of stomach diseases ulcer, appendix and trouble of disease	The water should be boiled and cooled before drinking, avoid fasting to take a light diet to used green vegetables in diet etc.
3	Women Diseases	Anemia the problem of uterus is caused mainly by early year.	To avoid early marriage intake of corn foods. Ex. Green vegetables, beet, groundnuts, sweet potatoes, apple, bananas, etc. in diet daily.
4	Malaria	This is caused by Mosquito bite and air pollution	Sleep in mosquito net, live smoking cigarettes.
5	Cancer	With chewing of tobacco, smoking cigarettes, expose to X-ray of gamma rays.	To avoid chewing tobacco and smoking cigarettes.
6	H.I.V.	Keep a physical relation without protection, take a blood without cheating, and use non-sterilized needles.	Take a checked blood before transfusion by doctors, use sterilized needles, use condom and motherhood after tested, avoid progeny positive mother.

Role of Social Workers:

After the diseases information we will see the work of the social workers which is following.

1. The research activity.
2. The social work done by project data collection and analysis.
3. Health education.
4. Demonstrator.
5. Neutralization development.
6. Arrange various health programs.
7. Museum development, Arrangement visit for medical student, social institution, Social house.

Conclusion:

This after the study of above information of paper we can conclude that the Civil Hospital of Solapur city, working very nicely in with consultation and provides good facility to the patients and peoples.

Suggestions:

1. The social workers should be providing facility in chip rate to poor people.
2. Patient should be a purchases antibiotic in with consultation doctors to avoid the diseases.
3. In Civil Hospital to provision of personal of patients with doctors.
4. There should be minimum crowd of people patient.
5. The people should give help to civil hospital from theirs his earning .

Reference Book:

- 1) National Human Research Development (1999-2002) – Planning Commission Government of India.